

Statement on education and scientific research in the field of therapeutic drug monitoring by the COST Action ENOTTA CA21147

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Abstract

The present article discusses and highlights the need for education and scientific research in the field of therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) through the prism of the COST Action on the European Network on Optimising Treatment with Therapeutic Antibodies in Chronic Inflammatory Diseases (ENOTTA). The overall hypothesis was that training schools and short-term scientific missions (STSM) would advance the field in areas with a high need for knowledge exchange.

Educational and research topics span the spectrum of the manufacturing of biological and personalized medicines, quality assurance, clinical research, regulatory approval, treatment evaluation, predicting therapeutic results via modeling, stratification of patients, assay of biologicals concentration in plasma, and cost-effectiveness of therapeutic drug monitoring.

In conclusion, we put forward that an educational program on TDM may be helpful in advancing the field and should include the aforementioned subjects. In addition, clinical application and interpretation in a variety of treatment areas should be presented in detail. Such a comprehensive educational program will respond to the requirements of best practices in TDM and future developments in the area.

Keywords

COST program, education, scientific research, therapeutic drug monitoring

Introduction

Therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) aims at ensuring that the right drug is used at the right dose for the right patient

(Spector et al. 1988). To achieve these goals, physicians and pharmacists need stratification of appropriate patients, standardization of assays, and individualized treatment guided by TDM (Gross 2001; Bluett et al. 2025; Eylenbosch

et al. 2025), performed in standardized laboratories (Skrede et al. 2024). Along this line, these are also the goals and objectives of the working groups (WG) of the European Network on Optimising Treatment with Therapeutic Antibodies in Chronic Inflammatory Diseases (ENOTTA), a European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) Action financed by the COST Association (www.cost.eu).

A COST Action provides a unique opportunity for junior and senior researchers and scientists to join networks engaging professionals from different scientific areas in European and neighboring countries. Part of these opportunities are the Short-Term Scientific Missions (STSM), training schools, webinars, and other forms of educational activities.

Within the COST Action ENOTTA, we previously assessed available educational programs on TDM and identified the need for a more structured education on TDM (Petrova et al. 2026).

The present article discusses and highlights the need for education and scientific research in the field of TDM through the prism of the COST Action ENOTTA. The overall hypothesis was that training schools and STSM would advance the field in areas with a high need for knowledge exchange.

Results

STSMs are an important and very useful tool for researchers to visit other universities or research institutions for scientific research purposes that can be fulfilled in a short period of time, i.e., not less than 1 month for young researchers and innovators (YRI) and not less than 1 week, in general, for advanced researchers, and cannot be longer than 3 months in both cases. The mobility of YRI is particularly encouraged and actively supported. In ENOTTA, a procedure for STSM applications was created in line with the requirements of the COST Association. Usually, the host proposes a research project, and interested candidates apply. However, interested candidates could also express

their interest in a research topic, which would then be announced on the ENOTTA website (<https://enotta.eu/grants/open-calls/>), along with those of the hosts.

During the first three grant periods of ENOTTA, 18 STSM took place (Table 1). As can be seen, the topics of the STSM vary from systematic reviews to assay methods, modeling studies, work with registries, and similar activities. Interest is oriented mostly toward biological medicines for inflammatory immune-mediated diseases and modeling techniques for therapeutic response prediction.

In addition to the STSM, in the same period, three training schools, 19 webinars, and two educational courses on the principles and practice of clinical and translational research, as well as on mathematical perspectives on immunobiology, took place. The training schools are organized primarily by the WG leaders and other main WG members and are hosted at leading institutions in Europe (Table 2). Furthermore, two 3-day courses were offered introducing clinical research processes and mathematical modeling (Table 2). The webinar series addressed gaps in knowledge, presenting a wealth of detailed information, in particular about TDM, related clinical procedures, and their practical application, in a live and on-demand manner, as all webinars were recorded and uploaded on the YouTube channel of ENOTTA (<https://www.youtube.com/@Cost.enotta>).

Collectively, Fig. 1 shows the educational activities within ENOTTA, organized by different institutions evenly distributed across participating countries.

Discussion and conclusion

In this work, we summarized topics of educational activities under the scheme of STSM, training schools, educational courses, and webinars as part of the COST Action ENOTTA. These topics span the spectrum of the manufacturing of biological and personalized medicines, quality assurance, clinical research, regulatory approval, treatment evaluation, predicting therapeutic

Table 1. STSM research topics.

Host country	Awardee country	Research topic
United Kingdom	Cyprus	Cost-effectiveness of TDM-guided vedolizumab treatment vs standard vedolizumab treatment for ulcerative colitis.
Bulgaria	Italy	A mechanistic mathematical model to describe the effect of methotrexate in reducing immunogenicity of adalimumab in axial spondyloarthritis.
Greece	Iceland	Sex-biased transcriptomic reprogramming in immune-related adverse events.
Italy	Iceland	Flow cytometric assessment of inflamed tissues in cardiovascular disease.
Sweden	Belgium	Population pharmacometrics model-based dose optimization of subcutaneous infliximab in inflammatory bowel disease.
Netherlands	Sweden	Collaboration with the Uppsala and Sanquin pharmacometrics team.
Netherlands	Belgium	Exploring the potential of a Belgian psoriasis registry: learnings from the BIOCAPTURE registry.
France	Czech Republic	The role of methotrexate metabolites in reducing immunogenicity of adalimumab in axial spondyloarthritis.
Iceland	Italy	Flow cytometric assessment of inflamed tissues in cardiovascular disease.
United Kingdom	Belgium	Towards individualized treatment in dermatology: a collaborative approach to model-informed precision dosing of therapeutic antibodies.
United Kingdom	Ireland	Leveraging bioinformatics for comprehensive analysis of patient data and sample availability in psoriasis research.
Türkiye	Tunisia	Systematic literature review of the differences between available therapeutic drug monitoring assays.
Belgium	Serbia	Characterization of exposure–response model for infliximab in patients with severe forms of inflammatory bowel diseases
Bulgaria	Poland	Systematic literature review of CEA analyses for TDM

Table 2. Training schools and webinars by organizing institution, subject, and goals.

Institution	Subject	Goals
Training schools		
University of Manchester, United Kingdom	Biomarkers training school	Provide a comprehensive, multidisciplinary understanding of biomarkers; explore their role in precision diagnosis and therapy; and dive into bioinformatics tools, emerging technologies, and ethical considerations.
KU Leuven, Ghent, Belgium.	Model-informed precision dosing	Focus on monoclonal antibody dosing in chronic immune-mediated inflammatory diseases.
University of Porto, Spain	Health economics and outcomes research (HEOR)	Equip participants with essential skills in health economics and the interpretation of pharmaco-economic data.
Educational courses		
Greek Scientists Society	Introduction to the principles and practice of clinical and translational research	Provide participants with a comprehensive understanding of the clinical research process and the various roles and responsibilities involved in conducting successful and ethical clinical research studies. Explain the clinical use of TDM of biologics in different pathologies.
Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	Workshop on mathematical perspectives on immunobiology	Mathematical modeling and computational analysis applied to immunology, host–pathogen interactions, onset, and progression in human diseases.
Webinars		
University Medical Centre in Ljubljana; Vrije Universiteit Brussel	Model-informed precision dosing (MIPD) of therapeutic antibodies in chronic inflammatory diseases	Overview of the available evidence for therapeutic drug monitoring in gastroenterology, an illustration of its current role in clinical practice, and an outline of potential future developments.
The University of Manchester, United Kingdom; University of Tours Hospital, France	Immune-mediated inflammatory diseases (IMIDs) (Pt. 2) and therapeutic antibodies vs. small molecules	Give a broad overview of the risk factors for developing IMIDs, their pathogenesis, advanced biologic therapies, and how immunogenicity affects response; explain how this variability can be studied by analyzing dose–concentration–effect relationships, the mechanisms of which are different from those of small molecules.
Medical University of Vienna, Austria; KU Leuven in Belgium	Therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM)	Explain the traditional concept of TDM, together with the opportunities and challenges of this approach. It additionally highlights new developments to enhance TDM and current scientific evidence on TDM.
University of Belgrade, Serbia; Polytechnic Institute of Porto, Lisbon	Dose stratification vs. therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM)	Exploring the advantages and challenges associated with proactive and reactive TDM; synthesize current evidence regarding the use of TDM for mAbs; and provide insights into the evolving landscape of personalized medicine in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) management.
Jagiellonian University, Medical College, Poland; KU Leuven, Belgium	Pharmacoeconomics and patient preferences in chronic inflammatory diseases	Expand knowledge and understanding of how patients perceive and value the attributes associated with both current and emerging treatments.
University of Poitiers, France; Uppsala University, Sweden	Pharmacometrics and model-informed precision dosing (MIPD)	Introducing basic pharmacometrics principles and pharmacometric models for the purposes of precision dosing of medicines.
Pharmacy Faculty of Lisbon University; Clinical Bioanalytics Laboratories at Sandoz	Regulatory and industry perspective on TDM/MIPD	Outlining the regulatory approval process, emphasizing clinical pharmacology studies and dose optimization required for regulatory compliance, illustrated with case examples involving, e.g., infliximab. Discuss the pharmaceutical industry's role, focusing on the optimization of analytical assays for clinical studies and their possible application in TDM.
University of Hamburg, Germany; InsightRX, San Francisco, California, USA	Software tools for MIPD	Model-informed precision dosing (MIPD) software leverages pharmacokinetic (PK) and pharmacodynamic (PD) models to optimize individualized medication dosing. After the presentations, the audience will be familiar with the underlying concept of MIPD, have seen case examples, and be introduced to challenges when using MIPD software.
Bellvitge University Hospital, Barcelona (Spain); University of Bergen, Norway	Experience with MIPD and the role of analytics	Presentation of the principles of analytical methods currently employed for serum concentrations of therapeutic antibodies. Present experience on the implementation of TDM and MIPD of biologics in inflammatory bowel disease.
Faculty of Medicine, University of Niš; Dokuz Eylül University, Türkiye	Artificial intelligence in TDM/MIPD	Artificial intelligence and machine learning have gained increasing popularity across disciplines in the last decade, but their application in MIPD remains in early stages, holding promise for the future.
Nutrition and Drug Research Department of the Institute of Public Health, Jagiellonian University, Medical College	Introduction to pharmacoeconomics	Provide an introductory overview of pharmacoeconomics to raise awareness of the importance of cost-effectiveness in the treatment of IMIDs and how to interpret such analyses. Practical examples of published cost-effectiveness studies in TDM are presented.
Health Insurance Organization Cyprus (HIO)	Introduction to health economics and outcomes research (HEOR)	Introduces fundamental concepts such as opportunity costs, trade-offs, and health utility measurement, encompassing direct and indirect methods. Discuss economic evaluation techniques, including cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA), cost-utility analysis (CUA), and incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICERs).
University of Manchester, United Kingdom	Clinical efficacy vs. effectiveness: ideal results vs. real-world impact	Summarize efficacy and clinical effectiveness, their similarities, and how they differ in context and scope, with examples from rheumatology.
University of Manchester, United Kingdom	Systematic review and meta-analysis	Cover the process of conducting systematic reviews and meta-analyses, including the formulation of research questions, literature search strategies, data extraction methods, and established frameworks.
Jagiellonian University, Medical College in Cracow, Poland	Optimizing therapy and personalizing treatment	Explores the role of TDM in enhancing the efficacy and safety of clinical treatments. Emphasize how TDM supports personalized medicine. Outline challenges in fixed-dose strategies and introduce TDM methodologies, including sample collection, analytical techniques, and real-time data interpretation.
Ankara University, Türkiye	Cost of illness, budget impact analysis	Present two essential methodologies in health economics: cost of illness (COI) and budget impact analysis (BIA).
Jagiellonian University in Kraków Medical University Sofia, Faculty of Pharmacy	Basics of stochastic thinking and Markov models	Introduce core modeling approaches in health economics, focusing on decision trees, Markov models, and partitioned survival models. Emphasize relevance for long-term and complex disease modeling.
MabDesign, France	Biologics: Industrial production of biopharmaceuticals	Explore key steps and challenges in large-scale manufacturing of biopharmaceuticals—from upstream development to downstream purification.
University of Manchester, United Kingdom	Markov models, simple practical examples	Present a simple Markov model technique for TDM.

Figure 1. Map of the training schools, webinars, and courses.

results via modeling, stratification of patients, assay of biologicals concentration in plasma, and cost-effectiveness of therapeutic drug monitoring.

In conclusion, we put forward that an educational program on TDM may be helpful in advancing the field and should include the aforementioned subjects. In addition, clinical application and interpretation in a variety of treatment areas should be presented in detail. Such a comprehensive educational program will respond to the requirements of best practices in TDM and future developments in the area (D'Angio et al. 1990; Gross 2001; Shenfield 2001).

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References

- Bluett J, Rumano M, Martínez Becerra MJ, Loeff F, Itik M, Ternant D, Desvignes C, Mulleman D, Skrede S (2025) Quality assessment of therapeutic drug monitoring assays of therapeutic antibodies across Europe: an update. *Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol* 137(5): e70129. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcpt.70129>
- D'Angio RG, Stevenson JG, Lively BT, Morgan JE (1990) Therapeutic drug monitoring: improved performance through educational intervention. *Therapeutic Drug Monitoring* 12(2): 173–181 <https://doi.org/10.1097/00007691-199003000-00011>
- Eylenbosch A, Wei R, Soenen R, Smith C, Standing JF, Mahil S, Lambert J (2025) From reactive to predictive: advancing biologic dosing in dermatology. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.70147>
- Gross AS (2001) Best practice in therapeutic drug monitoring. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 52(Suppl 1): 5S–10S. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2125.2001.0520s1005.x>
- Petrova G, Blagova S, Tachkov K, Santos M, Bluett J, Rumano M, Kkolou E, Drakalska E, Arev M, Barsbay MC, Mulleman D (2026) Therapeutic drug monitoring education: The current state. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 92(1): 198–209. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bcp.70252>
- Spector R, Park GD, Johnson GF, Vesell ES (1988) Therapeutic drug monitoring. *Clin Pharmacol Ther* 43(4): 345–353. <https://doi.org/10.1038/clpt.1988.42>
- Skrede S, Bogavac-Stanojević N, Dreesen E, Nielsen E, Zaninotto M, Mulleman D (2024) Therapeutic drug monitoring of monoclonal antibodies in chronic inflammatory diseases: A snapshot of laboratories and applications across Europe. *Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol* 134(4): 556–560. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcpt.13983>
- Shenfield GM (2001) Therapeutic drug monitoring beyond 2000. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 52(Suppl 1): 3S–4S. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2125.2001.0520s1003.x>

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main.